

POLYURETHANE FOAM CONTAINING ALGINATE HYDROGEL LOADED WITH EPIDERMAL GROWTH FACTOR

S. T. Oh, S.H. Kim, H. Y. Jung, J. M. Lee, and J. S. Park*

Department of Biosystems & Biomaterials Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, 151-742, Korea

* Corresponding author (jongshin@snu.ac.kr)

Keywords: *polyurethane, alginate, hydrogel, EGF, foam, wound, dressing*

1. Introduction

Polyurethane (PUs) is polymer with urethane linkages within the backbone and are prepared through the polyaddition polymerization between isocyanate and polyol [1]. PUs have been widely used in many areas such as fibers, elastomers, adhesives, and coatings due to their ingredient- and polymerization-dependent properties [2-3]. Though most PUs are hydrophobic, recent studies have reported hydrophilic PUs prepared by introducing hydrophilic functional groups to the soft-segment of the PU backbone. The most frequently used hydrophilic functional group is polyethylene glycol (PEG). The major application fields of these hydrophilic polyurethanes are membranes and wound dressings.

Hydrogels are hydrophilic, three-dimensional, expandable matrices that are produced through chemical and/or physical crosslinking of certain polymers. Hydrogels have been widely used as drug carriers in medical devices and pharmaceuticals. Recently, there has been an increased interest in the use of hydrogels in drug delivery systems (DDS) and tissue engineering due to their biocompatibility, ease of drug dispersion in a matrix, and high degree of control.

Sodium alginate (Na-alginate) is a linear polysaccharide copolymer composed of 1-4-linked β -D-mannuronic acid (M) and its c-5-epimer, α -L-guluronic acid (G), and is obtained primarily from brown seaweed. The amounts of (M) and (G) and their sequential distribution vary depending on the alginate source. Soluble sodium alginate can be transformed into a hydrogel through crosslinking with divalent cations (ex. Ca^{2+}).

The pKa value of the carboxyl group ranges between 3.4 and 4.4. In acidic conditions ($\text{pH} = 3 \sim 4$), the crosslinking is retained. In neutral or basic conditions ($\text{pH} \geq 7$), however, the crosslinking is broken due to the pKa characteristics of the carboxyl group. The broken crosslinking leads to the burst of the hydrogel, followed by release of the drug.

pH-sensitive alginate hydrogel containing polyurethane foam (AHP) was designed to allow for sustained protein drug release by preventing premature drug release in the acidic environment of the skin. This combination was anticipated to possess the strengths of both PU foam and hydrogel dressings.

In this study, the morphology of AHP was observed using SEM. Mechanical properties were investigated as a function of jute fiber content. The swelling ratios of PU foam were obtained. EGF release behavior from alginate hydrogel and AHP were investigated. In vitro test was studied using rat fibroblast cells.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Materials

Sodium alginate, PEG, glycerin, and 1, 4-butanediol (BDO) were used as polyols of polyurethane foam. To add flexibility to the foam, an aliphatic diisocyanate, 1, 6-hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI Wako Pure Chemical Industries Ltd., Japan), was used. Distilled water and dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL Lancaster, UK) were used as a foaming agent and a catalyst, respectively. PEG (molecular weight=2000) and PTMG (molecular weight=2000) were supplied by Shinyo Pure Chemicals Co., Ltd., Japan and Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA, respectively. Epidermal growth factor (EGF)

was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Inc, USA. All reagents, except Na-alginate, were used without purification. Jute fiber used as reinforcement was supplied by BNF Korea Co.,Ltd.

2.2 Preparation of AHP

The PU foam with EGF mixed hydrogel solution was placed in the vacuum chamber. The hydrogel penetrated into the foam due to the vacuum pressure. The hydrogel-containing PU foam was prepared in 0.3 M CaCl₂ solution, cured for 1h in the same solution, removed by filtration and washed with distilled water to remove excess CaCl₂(Figure 1).

Figure 1. The preparation method of AHP

2.3 Measurement and Analysis

2.3.1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis

The surface morphology of air-dried hydrogels was determined using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-5410 LV, JAPAN). Hydrogel samples were sputtered with gold and scanned at an accelerated voltage of 20 kv.

2.3.2. Compressive test

The Compressive test for each alginate hydrogel was performed according to ASTM D-638 with UTM (LRX plus, Lloyd Instruments, Ltd., US) at a strain rate of 10 mm/min.

2.3.3. Tensile test

The tensile test for each polyurethane foam was performed according to ASTM D-638 with UTM

(LRX plus, Lloyd Instruments, Ltd., US) at a strain rate of 10 mm/min.

2.3.4. Swelling properties of PTMG-based and PEG-based PU

Swelling ratios of PTMG-based PU and PEG-based PU foam were determined after soaking in water and cell culture media for 24 h.

2.3.5. Drug release behavior

To study the release profiles for the EGF-loaded alginate hydrogel and AHP, samples were immersed in a solution with a pH of 4.2, 5.2, 7.2, or 8.2. At predetermined time points, 800 μ l of this solution was taken out and analyzed by the Bradford method to measure the amount of released EGF at 562 nm using a spectrophotometer. The percentage of the cumulative amount of released EGF was determined using standard calibration curves.

2.3.6. In vitro test

Rat fibroblast cell cultures were maintained in a humidified 5% CO₂/95% air incubator at 37.5°C. The cells were routinely grown in 75 flasks in growth medium consisting of a combination of RPMI 1640, penicillin and streptomycin (stock conc. 100 IU/ml), glutamine (2 mM final conc.), HEPES (stock conc. 1 M, 15 mM final conc.), and serum FBS (10% final conc.). Filtration was performed through a 0.2-micron membrane. In order to evaluate in vitro the ability of samples to proliferate and differentiate fibroblast cell, fibroblast cells were cultured in the presence of a culture medium. At 24h post-seeding, each group was treated with EGF, EGF-loaded alginate hydrogel and EGF-loaded alginate hydrogel containing PU foam (Figure 12). After 2day, fibroblast cell proliferation ratio was evaluated by MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide, Sigma-Aldrich) biochemical assay. the culture medium was replaced with 100 μ l of MTT solution and the well plate was incubated for 4 h at 37°C in 5% CO₂. Absorbance was measured using a reader (test wavelength: 570nm; reference wavelength: 630nm). All the tests were performed in triplicate. The cell shape was observed using an optical microscope (CSB-HP5, Samwon, Korea) that was equipped with a CCD-camera (WAT-202B, Watec, Japan). PU foams were tested after disinfection using 70 vol.% ethanol

(in distilled water) for 30 min, dipping in distilled water for 48 h and sterilization by ultraviolet irradiation for 20 min (10 min per side). Fibroblast cell-only was used as a negative control.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis

Figures 2 show cross-sectional images of PU foam combined with hydrogel. These pictures illustrate that the hydrogel penetrated evenly into the PU foam. There were many pores in the PU foam (circular shaped) and many hydrogels were penetrated evenly into these PU pores, which look like leaves. These hydrogels look brighter than the PU foam pores because hydrogel contains a large amount of water.

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of cross-sectional images (a) AHP ($\times 35$) and (b) AHP ($\times 100$).

3.2. Compressive test

To investigate the reinforce effect of natural fiber on the mechanical properties of alginate hydrogel, compressive test was performed with different jute fiber content of 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 4.0 w/w%. Table 1 shows the compressive properties of alginate hydrogel as a function of jute fiber content. Overall, the compressive properties were highly improved than alginate only hydrogel.

Jute content (w/w%)	Young's modulus (KPa)	Breaking stress (KPa)	Breaking strain (%)	Fracture energy (J)
0 (alginate only)	4.2	2.9	49.1	0.142
0.25	8.6	5.1	59.3	0.302
0.5	11.3	7.2	63.7	0.458
1.0	16.5	10.2	71.2	0.726
1.5	16.3	10.1	70.6	0.712
2.0	17.1	10.8	69.1	0.746
4.0	17.2	10.7	62.2	0.665

Table 1. Compressive properties of alginate hydrogel as a function of jute content.

3.3 Tensile test

In general, the mechanical properties of hydrogels containing PU foams were decreased as compared with those of PU foam only.

Figure 3. Tensile properties of PU foams only and hydrogel-containing PU foams.

3.4. Swelling properties of PTMG-based and PEG-based PU

Figure 4 shows the effect of foam hydrophilicity on its swelling ratio. PTMG-based PU foam has hydrophobic surface while PEG-based PU foam has hydrophilic surface due to their chemical structure. The water swelling ratio of PEG-based PU foam was 15.4, while that of PTMG-based one was 0.94.

The media swelling ratio of PEG-based PU foam was also much higher as a value of 14.7, while that of PTMG-based one was 0.98. The swelling ratios of water and media were similar. This result indicates that PEG-based PU foam is highly water absorptive enough to fulfill the requirement of commercial dressings.

Figure 4. Swelling ratio of PTMG-based PU and PEG-based PU foam in respect of water and cell culture media [each data point is mean \pm S.E. (standard error)].

3.5. Drug release behavior

Figure 5 shows EGF release profiles from alginate hydrogel and AHP at four different pH conditions: 4.2, 5.2 (normal skin), 7.2, and 8.2 (wound area). As shown in Figure 37, the cumulative release increased rapidly with time and reached an equilibrium value after a certain time. The equilibrium value was the highest at pH=8.2 and the lowest at pH=4.2. The initial slope of the curve, which is a measure of the release rate, was highest at pH=8.2 and lowest at pH=4.2. In general, the release behavior of EGF was similar with that of BSA since both of these drugs are protein drug. However, EGF release rate from alginate hydrogel only and AHP was different. EGF release rate from AHP was slower than that from alginate hydrogel because of its composite structure.

Figure 5. Release profiles of EGF from (a) alginate hydrogel only and (b) alginate hydrogel-containing PU foam at various pH values.

3.6. In vitro test

EGF-treated, EGF-loaded alginate hydrogel, and EGF-loaded AHP cells were proliferated 2.7, 2.5, and 2.2 times compared with cell only group, respectively (Figure 6). Figure 7 shows that AHP treated well group was much more packed with cells than cell only group only. However, EGF-treated cells were the most proliferated, hydrogel-treated cells were the next, and AHP-treated cells were the last order.

Figure 6. In-vitro test using rat fibroblast cell for 48 h.

Figure 7. In-vitro test of rat fibroblast cell (a) the cells grown in cell culture media only, (b) the cells grown in EGF-loaded AHP treated media for 48 h.

- [1] Kwon JY and Kim HD, Preparation and properties of crosslinkable waterborne polyurethanes containing aminoplast -Effect of curing condition-. *Fibers and Polymers*, 7(2):95-104, 2006.
- [2] Seo WJ, Sung YT, Han SJ, Kim YH, Ryu OH, Lee HS, and Kim WN. Synthesis and properties of polyurethane/clay nanocomposite by clay modified with polymeric methane diisocyanate. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 101(5):2879-2883, 2006.
- [3] Liu Y, Ni Y, and Zheng S. polyurethane Networks Modified with Octa(propylglycidyl ether) Polyhedral Oligomeric Silsesquioxane. *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics*, 207(20):1842-1851, 2006.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (R11-2005-065).

References